

The Ministry of Time: Coordinating Societal Rhythms through Automation

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Abstract

How will time be conceptualized in the future? Ministry of Time is a futuristic concept derived from anticipatory anthropology, which emerged in the ethnographic research in Poland conducted in the project "Choreography of time: Cultural practices of time management". The project involved 60 interviews about time management. We live in a society with many rhythms. In everyday life, we often have to navigate between conflicting and uncoordinated time frames. Furthermore, leisure time is inequitably distributed in many societies. As a result of this situation, all the consequences are transferred to the individual. The way we deal with the constant lack of time and acceleration is up to each of us. To deal with desynchronized time rhythms, many of my interviewees dream of automating their time management decisions. The idea is that AI can guide them to better decisions by learning their human behavior. A „digital assistant” could help them organize their lives. „Intelligent software” could decide what is urgent and important. The Ministry of Time is a future idea that emerged from interviews. As a result of the time policy, the Ministry would coordinate and synchronize social time on a systemic level: specify the hours when offices are available, as well as the working, consumption, and rest hours. Organize them so that they don't interfere with each other as they

currently do. It would gather data about individuals' time and manage system time for the Ministry using automated decision-making. Ministry of Time has been found to be useful by my interlocutors. Traffic jams are created by common working hours, which causes overlapping time rhythms. Services, such as medical clinics, stores, offices, and museums, are open during working hours. How does all of this make sense? A desire to change these rhythms led to the idea of the Ministry of Time. However, my interlocutors also see the dangers of this approach. The Ministry of Time will construct temporal behavioral patterns and steer society's time. Some people may feel uncomfortable when they realize that they are entrusting so much power to algorithms. Their concern is that they may violate their privacy. A lack of trust in these systems' objectivity and their usage of data is not unjustified. The algorithms used by social networks provide a good example of the dangers associated with data collection mechanisms built into applications. The usage of this data to shape opinions and personalize advertising is already widely known. It is to be expected that the data collected by our virtual assistant on our time organization patterns will also be subject to trade in the era of cognitive capitalism. In my presentation, I will discuss the opportunities and risks of applying automated decision making to social time coordination. In addition, I will explore whether people are willing to surrender control to an outside entity in favor of intelligent time management and social time algorithms.

Key words

anticipatory anthropology, automated decision-making systems, social time coordination, Artificial Intelligence, time management, ministry of time, ethical implications of ai, privacy concerns in ai systems, digital temporal architecture, algorithmic governance, societal rhythms

Introduction

This article introduces 'the Ministry of Time', a futuristic concept derived from anticipatory anthropology that emerged from ethnographic research conducted in Poland. This research was part of two interlinked projects: 'Choreography of Time: Cultural Practices of Time Management,' which gathered extensive data for analysis, and 'AUTO-WELF: Automating Welfare – Algorithmic Infrastructures for Human Flourishing in Europe,' which not only funded the study but also provided an additional analytical framework. The 'Choreography of Time' project involved 60 interviews focused on individual time management practices and provided a fertile ground for exploring the philosophical, sociological, and anthropological implications of artificial intelligence (AI) and automated decision-making

systems on our perception and construction of social time. The discussion navigates the intricate interplay between rapid technological advancements and established societal rhythms, aiming to illuminate the evolving landscape of time in our increasingly digital era.

Research questions

The intricate concept of the Ministry of Time prompts a series of critical inquiries into the automation of social time and its broader implications. Firstly, the feasibility of automating social time itself raises fundamental questions about the nature of time as both a measurable and a perceptual entity. Can we, indeed, automate social time and our interactions in time? This leads to a deeper exploration of how automation may alter our conceptualization of time. How might automation change human temporality? As digital tools increasingly mediate our daily schedules and time management practices, it is essential to investigate whether these tools enhance our temporal autonomy or lead to a more rigid structuring of time imposed by algorithmic control.

This investigation delves into how AI and automated, algorithmic systems could transform our traditional understanding of time. The potential for AI to change how we think about and experience time invites us to consider scenarios where time may be perceived not just linearly (strongly determined and structured) (Mumford 1934, Thompson 1967), and also not pointillist (unstructured and undetermined) (Bauman 2000, 2017). AI perhaps can change our perception of time into something in between—more open than linear time and more structured than chaotic pointillist time. Towards this idea, as I propose at the end of this paper with the Graph, a geometrical metaphor of time visualizes time as a network. To reach the final presentation of the graph concept, this article tries to examine the implications of algorithmic infrastructures on human temporality—how the rhythm of human and societal life adjusts in response to the capabilities and demands of automated systems.

A vital aspect of this research focuses on the social organization of time in the area of automation. Automation could lead to significant shifts in how societies organize, experience, and value time. How will these changes impact various aspects of daily life, such as work, leisure, and social interactions? If social time can be automated, what mechanisms would be required, and what ethical considerations arise from such an endeavor? These questions are pivotal as they explore the broader ramifications of living in a world where time is not just a backdrop but an actively managed resource. This research aims to uncover whether our future will align more closely with a utopian vision of enhanced freedom and productivity

or veer towards dystopian outcomes where time becomes a commodity strictly governed by algorithmical systems.

Theoretical framework

The theoretical scaffolding of this paper is built upon two foundational frameworks: the critical time studies, spanning from iTime to aiTime, and critical algorithm studies, focusing on automated decision-making systems and artificial intelligence.

Critical time studies – from iTime to aiTime

The first pillar of our theoretical framework is the field of critical time studies. This field aims to understand the various ways time is constructed, valued, experienced, and exploited among different social groups, for whom time has become a domain of exploitation, and time regimes are used to sustain deeply rooted patterns of power and inequality (Pickering 2004; Sabelis 2007). Researchers in this field examine the tense relationships between time, power, and social inequalities, including disparities in access to leisure time, freedom to manage one's own time, and control over time (Strzelecka 2021a; 2021b; 2022). Concepts such as network time (Sugarman, Thrift 2017; Hassan 2009; Hassan, Purser 2007), also known in literature as digital time (Barker 2011, 2012), and iTime (Agger 2011), are integral to this discourse. The concept of iTime highlights the critical role of computer programs, mobile applications, and smartphones, defining a postmodern time that is not limited like clock time (based on clock hands) or natural time (based on sunrises and sunsets). This new kind of time is mobile, portable, and flexible, challenging boundaries that existed before the internet era: between public and private, day and night, work and leisure, space and time. iTime is based on unrelated elements, which leads to variance with the biorhythm of the human organism. Utilizing the critical achievements of time studies, I seek a form of time that would counteract harmful desynchronization (Rosa, 2003, 2013), social acceleration (Davis, 2013; Tomlinson, 2007; Cifric, 2010), and sensory deprivation (Virilio, 1986, 1995, 2000), anticipating if this is what aiTime could be.

Critical algorithm studies – from Automative decision makking systems to Artificial intelgence

The second pillar of our theoretical framework is Critical Algorithm Studies (Bucher 2018; Eubanks 2018; Gillespie 2014). This domain seeks to unravel the societal challenges

posed by data science, algorithms, automated decision-making systems (ADM), and artificial intelligence (AI)¹. This framework delves into issues such as bias, opacity in data access and infrastructure, and representation.

It critically examines how algorithms are inherently political, their capacity to wield power, and their role in constructing social realities, thereby reflecting and preserving existing power relations and social conditions. Researchers in this field explore the various ways in which algorithms condition the social world, highlighting the significance of their deployment and the ends they serve. According to Richardson (2022), AI and ADS function similarly to laws by constructing social reality in ways that maintain existing power dynamics.

Critical Algorithm Studies is an interdisciplinary field that examines the social, ethical, and political implications of algorithms and their applications. Key points include:

- Algorithms have embedded values and make choices that have social consequences. Critical Algorithm Studies analyze these choices and their impacts.
- The aim is to systematically study and address the legal, ethical, and social challenges posed by data science, including issues of bias, limited data access, and infrastructure representation.
- The goal is to better understand the impact of algorithms on social life, power relations, ethics, and responsibility, investigating where and how algorithms fail or dominate.

By integrating Critical Time Studies with Critical Algorithm Studies, this article aims to analyze the automation processes in decision-making related to time. This exploration asserts that AI and ADS are socio-technical systems which, to be effective, must adapt to and resonate with the contextual settings in which they operate. This combined framework provides a robust basis for dissecting the complexities of temporal management in the digital age, offering insights into the potential futures molded by new technologies.

¹ ADM and AI – categorical terms used to refer to the suite of 'big data' technologies and applications for legal and regulatory purposes (Richardson 2022: 787). The term 'automated decision system' means 'a computational process, including one derived from machine learning, statistics, or other data processing or artificial intelligence techniques, that makes a decision or facilitates human decision making, that impacts persons.' (Automated Decision Systems Accountability Act, A.B. 2269, 2019–2020 Reg. Sess. (Cal. 2020); 'computerized implementations of algorithms, including those derived from machine learning or other data processing or artificial intelligence techniques, which are used to make or assist in making decisions.' (Int. No. 1696-A, Law No. 2018/049 (N.Y.C. Council, enacted Jan. 11, 2018); or 'An AI system is a machine-based system that can, for a given set of human-defined objectives, make predictions, recommendations, or decisions influencing real or virtual environments.' (OECD, Recommendation of the Council on Artificial Intelligence, OECD/LEGAL/0449, at 7 (2021) (cited in: Richardson 2022). 'Automated Decision Systems' are any systems, software, or processes that use computation to aid or replace government decisions, judgments, and/or policy implementation that impact opportunities, access, liberties, rights, and/or safety. Automated Decision Systems can involve predicting, classifying, optimizing, identifying, and/or recommending' (Richardson 2022: 795).

Literature review

At the intersection of the two theoretical frameworks outlined in this paper, Judy Wajcman's article, "The Digital Architecture of Time Management" (Wajcman, 2018), stands out. It focuses on the Timeful app, an electronic calendar designed to transform time management by shifting from a passive event repository to an active, intelligent planning system. This system leverages algorithms to offer customized advice for daily life organization, learning from the user's schedule, habits, and needs.

To delve deep into the local culture of the app's creators, Wajcman relocated to Silicon Valley. She conducted interviews with the Timeful team and other digital calendar teams, including software engineers, digital application designers, producers, and product managers. Over the years 2017-2018, Wajcman interviewed 22 individuals living and working in Silicon Valley, supplemented by numerous other conversations with a broad range of technology industry professionals.

Wajcman aimed to explore the digital architecture of calendars and the methods they employ to manage temporal relations. The topics discussed included work practices, time management strategies, motivations for software creation, the appeal of various platforms, and user experiences, alongside the creation process and planning algorithms. She concluded that the real goal behind the development of digital calendar systems is the mechanization of human thought and actions to make them more efficient and reliable, as well as to strengthen the socio-cultural hegemony of quantitative time understanding.

Thus, Wajcman's article goes beyond merely describing the digital architecture of time management. It presents an interpretation of this phenomenon within the scope of critical time studies and the biopolitics of temporality, offering a critical perspective on how time management applications might influence our conceptualization and experience of time in the digital age.

Methodological approach

Ethnographic methodology

The research involved broader ethnographic methodology conducting in-depth interviews and desk research based on observing social media to explore the topic of AI time management. My anticipatory anthropology method procedure started in 2019, when I conducted 60 in-depth interviews across Poland. Poland was chosen as the location for

conducting the research presented in this article for a compelling reason: Poland's socio-economic transition from a post-communist state to a neoliberal economy has led to significant shifts in time management practices and societal rhythms (Strzelecka 2021a). This transition has created a unique context for exploring how automation and digital technologies could further transform time management in a society already undergoing rapid change. These interviews were pivotal in understanding individual experiences with time management within various work environments and were instrumental in shaping the speculative ideas about the Ministry of Time².

In the study, data were derived primarily from two segments of the questionnaire³ titled "Technology" and "System Time." The "System Time" section was specifically designed to access knowledge about the real practices that coordinate and desynchronize individual temporality in relation to societal norms and social rhythms. I explored strategies and tactics for coping with differing rhythms and efforts to align individual time with systemic societal time. From the data collected, insights were gained on the synchronization of various social times and attempts to "tame" them through systemic solutions, emphasizing that societies could not function without numerous measures aimed at standardizing time (Gurvitch 1964: 31–33). This section also helped identify which systemic temporalities were out of sync but should be synchronized, leading to discussions about the feeling of desynchronization among different social time rhythms and a general sense of time scarcity.

The "Technology" section aimed to understand which time management applications the respondents used and how they experienced themselves through the lens of new technologies⁴. Employing anticipatory anthropology methodology, I asked respondents what expectations current technologies failed to meet and what features they hoped these technologies would offer in the future. Questions such as "How should such an application work? Imagine that you are using an application, a program, or a device that makes it easier for you to control your time. What functions does this program have that you consider useful?"

² Respondents varied in their work settings—some worked from home, others in office environments, with some having flexible work hours and others adhering to fixed schedules set by employers. The diversity of these settings provided a rich tapestry of time management practices and perceptions. Interviews were conducted both face-to-face and via online platforms such as Skype and Zoom, depending on respondents' availability and preference, ensuring a broad representation of perspectives. The participants, all born between 1980 and 2000, grew up with the rise of the internet but did not use smartphones in their formative years. They reside in Warsaw, Krakow, Gdansk, Wroclaw, and Poznan—Poland's largest, fast-paced cities, which were considered most suitable for exploring time management technologies.

³ The interview questionnaire can be viewed at the website: <https://choreography-of-time.weebly.com/uploads/6/7/7/5/67758073/questionnaire.pdf>

⁴ Some of the results from this section of the questionnaire were presented in the article 'Time Paradoxes of Neoliberalism: How Time Management Applications Change the Way We Live' (Strzelecka 2022).

encouraged respondents to imagine the ideal device that would fulfill their dreams regarding time and its management. This approach facilitated gathering their visions about future applications where big data and artificial intelligence play significant roles, leading to creative speculations about desirable data futures. Respondents articulated their unmet needs in time management, revealing their aspirations for future technological innovations.

To stay current with technology related to AI and time management, I continued to observe the topic of algorithmic time management through social media following the conducted research. This observation of the subject continued until the beginning of 2024. My exploration not only provided a practical perspective on current technology use but also opened a window into the potential future developments in time management technologies.

Anticipatory anthropology

In developing the speculative concept of the Ministry of Time, my methodological approach was deeply rooted in anticipatory anthropology, a fusion of cultural anthropology and futurology (Strzelecka 2013). The term 'anticipatory anthropology' was coined by Robert Textor (Textor 1985, 1999, 2009). He argued that an anticipatory dimension should be developed within anthropology to enhance its capacity to (1) explain sociocultural change and (2) contribute to the making of effective proactive public policy (Textor 1985). This approach is instrumental in forecasting cultural futures by critically analyzing contemporary cultural trends, societal hopes, and fears. It leverages anthropologists' ability to discern underlying cultural patterns and potential societal shifts before they fully manifest, thus preparing societies for future changes.

As Textor mentioned, "By 'anticipatory anthropology' we mean the use of anthropological knowledge and ethnographic methods, appropriately modified and focused, to anticipate change. We take the position that the time has come for cultural anthropology to add an anticipatory dimension to its long-existing and successful historical, descriptive, interpretive, comparative, and social-science-generalizing dimensions. The results of an anticipatory anthropology project ought, in most cases, to facilitate the development of public policy that will be proactive rather than reactive" (Textor 1985: 4).

An important application of anticipatory anthropology, relevant to this article, is its suitability for analyzing the relations between social dynamics and technologies. As Laughlin (2021: 171) states, "An important application of anticipatory anthropology is to analyze the relations between social relations and technologies and, based upon the changes in these

relations in the past, to anticipate future scenarios that may arise because of new technologies. For instance, given what we know about changes in labor opportunities due to advances in AI, what are the likely implications of self-driving vehicles, smart warehouses, or medical diagnostic devices?"

For this study, anticipatory anthropology was pivotal in understanding the implications of artificial intelligence (AI) and automated systems on temporal management and our interactions with time. The insights gained from the interviews significantly contributed to the development of the speculative concept of the Ministry of Time. This methodological grounding facilitated a robust examination of how digital technologies, particularly AI and automated decision-making systems, are transforming our interactions with time. It provided a nuanced understanding of potential future scenarios and their societal impacts. By envisaging future scenarios during the research process, anticipatory anthropology offered a framework for understanding not only the present conditions but also the possible future states—enabling a dynamic exploration of how society might navigate and negotiate the complexities of time in an increasingly automated world.

The Dynamics of Time in the Age of Automation

The development of new technologies has made time digitally compressed, and it no longer flows in a traditional, linear, event-based sequence. Network simultaneity allows an event in one part of the world, once digitized, to have almost instantaneous global effects. The ability to transmit information at the speed of light has led to an experience of simultaneous and immediate availability, replacing sequence and duration. Electronic information is organized in loosely structured and flexibly changing networks, leading to the emergence of what I describe with my coined term, "Insta(nt) time," known in the literature also as multi-temporality (Barker 2011, 2012), pointillist time (Bauman 2000, 2017), heterotemporality (Hutchings 2008: 160–176), timeless time (Castells 1996, 2012), and poly-rhythm (Appadurai, 1996).

The complexity of multitemporal social times has necessitated the creation of various systems, marked by efforts to accelerate specific temporal processes through automation. Automated systems are specifically designed to speed up operations. Originally, automation aimed primarily at hastening these processes to assist in faster task execution and enable effective functioning within fast-paced modern societies. These systems are burdened with the promise of automating and simplifying life in complex heterotemporal times.

To illustrate how we automate time, one of the earliest examples of time-related systems observed with automation involves the notable acceleration of workplace tasks. Nowadays this includes the automation of administrative duties, office workflows, and meticulous time tracking and recording using advanced technology and software. These systems accurately log hours spent on different tasks, projects, and work processes, optimizing efficiency. Another example is the judicial sector, where automation is used to handling times. Initially, automation was expected to expedite case resolutions and allocate them more efficiently based on staff workloads. Beyond the judiciary, ADM finds application in healthcare, social services, and policing, among other public sectors (e.g., Brown et al., 2019; Dencik et al., 2018). Another example of automation that affects time is the automation within agriculture, particularly precision farming. Here, automation influences the timing, pace, rhythm, and seasonality of crop production. AI technologies have altered agricultural timings, enhancing food production rates per capita and thereby enabling more people to live in urban settings and engage in other capital-generating activities.

The theoretical advantages of automation include addressing the pervasive issue of time scarcity, ostensibly freeing up human time for other endeavors. Authors like Bastani (2018) in 'Fully Automated Luxury Communism: A Manifesto' view automation as a potential liberator of human time. However, there are theoretical risks such as quality degradation, the introduction of errors, and delays in critical, in-depth actions. For example, modern precision agriculture allows many to forego traditional farming, but this shift has not liberated time without significant trade-offs, such as deterioration in food quality. Promises of time savings often end up being counterproductive, exacerbating the very issues they aim to solve.

Findings: The Need for Coordination of Social Rhythms

In a society filled with diverse social rhythms, many are uncoordinated and conflicting. In everyday life, we often navigate between these unsynchronized time frames. Many of these rhythms are subjected to automation in an attempt to coordinate them, yet according to my interlocutors, many more should also be synchronized. In this section, I will present examples of areas currently lacking coordination around time and those that should be synchronized.

Daily Life Dissonance: Misaligned Shopping Hours and Work Schedules

The first example of mismatched rhythms mentioned by my interlocutors concerns the opening hours of stores. These small shops in Poland usually operate from 10:00 AM to 6:00

PM, coinciding with the typical work hours of most people. This overlap results in massive queues at supermarkets that remain open until late in the evening, sometimes even until 10:00 PM. "So why haven't any of the small stores decided to change their hours to 4:00 PM to 9:00 PM?" Such an arrangement would indeed make more sense, allowing working individuals to avoid wasting time in queues after work.

Healthcare Hours Accessibility

Healthcare hours accessibility represents another critical area where my research highlights the misalignment between doctors' opening hours and typical working hours. Medical appointments are predominantly scheduled during standard working hours, often requiring patients to take leave from work and use up valuable holiday time for medical visits. This arrangement seems inefficient and underscores the need for a more flexible scheduling system that could better accommodate the working public's availability. My interlocutors express surprise and frustration that visiting a doctor often necessitates taking a day off work, consuming the limited holiday time that is treated with great care in Poland. As a result, people use their holiday days not for relaxation, but to stand in queues at medical offices.

Public Administration Hours

Observing the various rhythms of society, it becomes apparent that numerous areas are misaligned and clash with each other, creating situations that could critically be considered absurd. These discrepancies are often culturally specific; for example, in Poland, most government offices and other public services are open during the working hours of most citizens, necessitating time off work for many to access services.

Transportation and Traffic Management

Transport sectors have begun to address timing inefficiencies through integrated dynamic transit information systems like those in Gdańsk. Additionally, traffic light control algorithms are being implemented to better manage the flow of vehicles. Despite these efforts, significant traffic congestion persists, exacerbated by peak working hours. One interviewee mentioned how he strategically avoids traffic by adjusting his departure times, a personal workaround to a systemic issue. However, this is not always possible: "There are certain inevitabilities, for instance, having to drive my children to school at a specific time. Then I am dependent on there being rush hours, and I might spend an extra thirty minutes stuck in traffic."

The discussions with my interviewees underscored how various services—public administration, healthcare, retail, and transportation—are misaligned with the majority's working hours. While the concept of automating the synchronization of these societal rhythms seems complex and currently unfeasible on a large scale, the necessity for such coordination, *inter alia* through automation, was highlighted during the discussions. My interlocutors imagined future scenarios where time management is automated. One such proposal that emerged during our conversations is the Ministry of Time, which I will discuss in the next section.

The Ministry of Time: Digital Government of Social Rhythms

The Ministry of Time is a concept derived from anticipatory anthropology and was developed through interviews suggesting a future where the synchronization of societal rhythms could be centrally managed. This initiative of central coordination and automation is envisioned to regulate the operating hours of public offices, work hours, consumption periods, and rest times in a manner that ensures no conflicting schedules. By managing and coordinating the time of citizens efficiently, it could alleviate mismatches that currently exist in society, potentially harmonizing various sectors such as healthcare, public administration, and retail to operate more synchronously with people's lives. The envisioned 'Ministry of Time' exemplifies a future concept where central management of societal rhythms could potentially alleviate mismatches that are currently prevalent across various sectors including public administration, healthcare, retail, and transportation. The idea of the Ministry of Time emerged from in-depth discussions during my research, illustrating the potential of using time as a tool for coordination and the automation of social multi-dimensional time.

The Function and Rationale for the Emergence of the Ministry of Time

The Ministry of Time would emerge from public policies aimed at using time as a tool for temporal social engineering, envisioned as a regulatory body capable of effectively steering society by holding data on most citizens' schedules. This concept involves the intelligent automated decision-making system to manage timings effectively. By organizing the operating hours of public offices and setting work, consumption, and rest periods, the ministry aims to ensure no conflicts arise, thereby optimizing societal functioning in an equitable manner that is not influenced by any specific social or interest groups. Such coordination could resolve issues like traffic jams and long waits in queues, which stem from uncoordinated work and service

hours. By altering these rhythms, the ministry could facilitate a more rational and unbiased distribution of active hours, potentially making society function more smoothly. For instance, aligning service availability with varied personal schedules could reduce peak-time pressures and distribute activities more evenly throughout the day, significantly alleviating daily inefficiencies and the stress of managing personal schedules against rigid institutional timings.

The Ministry of Time as a Grand Futuristic Proposal on Time and AI

Ultimately, the Ministry of Time represents a grand futuristic proposal concerning the management and automation of time through AI. This initiative reflects a profound intersection of technology and everyday life where AI does not merely assist but potentially overtakes the management of time itself. It suggests a future where our daily rhythms might be dictated by algorithmic design. This could lead to a significant transformation in how we perceive and interact with time in our modern society. The Ministry of Time is envisioned as a systematic effort to coordinate and automate social rhythms. This ministry would regulate the operating hours of public offices and set work, consumption, and rest periods to ensure they do not conflict. By managing and coordinating the time of citizens efficiently, it could alleviate the mismatches that currently exist, potentially harmonizing sectors like healthcare, public administration, and retail to operate more synchronously with people's lives. Moreover, envisioning a world with a Ministry of Time invites us to consider a system where time is not just a backdrop for action but a central element of policy and everyday life, actively managed to foster a more synchronized society. This radical rethinking proposes a future where daily rhythms might be dictated by a mix of organizational needs and advanced technology, aiming for utopian efficiency yet also sparking debates on the dystopian risks of such a tightly controlled societal structure.

Imagined Applications: Envisioning the Future of AI in Time Management

Throughout my research, interviewees shared their visions for AI applications to automate time management for enhanced life organization. They imagine sophisticated tools leveraging artificial intelligence, ranging from simple yet powerful applications to seemingly unreal technologies that optimize daily schedules and life decisions. Surprisingly often, interviewees are willing to surrender control to an external entity for intelligent time management and social time algorithms. These ideas align with the concept of automated decision-making processes in time management. According to some interviewees, the solution

to the current inconsistency of time is to intensify technological solutions through the coordination of time with AI.

Proposed Future Applications for AI Automation in Time Management:

1. **Time Stopping Button:** An imaginative concept where individuals could pause time, thereby extending crucial deadlines or prolonging cherished moments.
2. **Augmented Reality Voice Assistant:** A tool that integrates with real-world interactions to provide contextual advice on time management and on-the-go scheduling.
3. **Mental Timer:** A mental alert system designed to help users monitor and manage the time spent on specific tasks, enhancing focus and productivity.
4. **Time Calculator:** An app that analyzes optimal time allocation based on personal productivity patterns and external deadlines.
5. **AI Decision-Maker:** Employs AI to prioritize tasks and manage distractions, aiming to guide users to better decision-making by learning from their behavior.
6. **Time Reversal Device:** A speculative device that allows users to undo past actions, illustrating the human wish to correct mistakes retrospectively.
7. **Temporal Bubble:** A sophisticated concept that manipulates time within a controlled environment, allowing for different time speeds to optimize various activities.
8. **Digital Assistant:** A general tool to help individuals organize their lives more efficiently.
9. **Intelligent Software:** Designed to determine urgency and importance, guiding task prioritization and day-to-day decisions.

These envisioned applications and tools reflect a deep-seated desire to harness technology not only to enhance personal efficiency but also to tackle broader issues of coordination in daily life amidst asynchronous societal rhythms. To address desynchronized time rhythms, many of my interviewees dream of automating their time management decisions, emphasizing the potential efficiencies gained from synchronizing various times. These applications are imagined to operate at a level of automation profound enough to completely replace human involvement in tasks related to scheduling, coordinating, and remembering. The

envisioned tools are superintelligent and superrational time-management systems, fully taking over decision-making and priority setting.

The realization of these visions would fundamentally alter our approach to time management and reshape our perception of time itself. These potential applications could drastically change our interactions with time. Merely contemplating these innovations suggests a significant shift in our temporal understanding, indicating a future transformation. These envisioned applications and tools represent a future where automated systems revolutionize how we manage time. This initial reflection highlights a cultural shift we are beginning to witness, transforming our perception and prioritization of temporal experiences.

Indeed, the seeds of such solutions have begun to appear. Examples can be seen in advertisements. The main keywords used in the context of presenting these graphical materials advertising AI-powered time management applications include: workflow, productivity, effectiveness, taking over mundane, repetitive tasks, facilitating decision-making processes, and freeing up employees' time for more challenging and innovative projects.

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	Mon 17	Tue 18	Wed 19	Thu 20	Fri 21
10 AM	Prep for design meeting				
11 AM	Team sync	Team sync	Team sync	Blog post images	Gym
12 PM	Update product roadmap			Kickoff with Acme	
1 PM	Lunch	Coffee chat with Jane	Respond to emails	Gym	1:1 (Amy <-> John)
2 PM	Draft marketing strategy	Prep for design meeting		Lunch	
3 PM	Investor Call	Lunch	Review website iterations	Draft marketing strategy	
4 PM	Check emails	Build landing page	Strategy session with Acme	Ad graphics	
	1:1 (Sarah <-> John)	1:1 (James <-> John)	1:1 (Matt <-> John)		
	Leadership meeting	QA feature release	Website design review		
	Write copy for ads			30 min Dentist	
		Gym		30 min	
		UI project sync			

Behavioral Algorithms and Time Management: The Case of Timeful

Applications like Timeful, discussed in Judy Wajcman's article, aim to blend behavioral economics with optimization algorithms to not just measure time but also guide how people manage their schedules (Wajcman 2018). These applications monitor user activity, measure time spent on various tasks, and collect vast amounts of personal data necessary for intelligent time management. By employing machine learning, such apps can "nudge" users toward making better decisions. As the creator of Timeful explained, aiming to create an intelligent planning system: "There is no doubt that we will receive much more algorithmic advice in various areas of our lives. Time is one of those frontiers."

The idea behind Timeful is to integrate behavioral economics with optimization algorithms. It serves not only to measure time but also to gather data on how people manage their time. It tracks user activities, measures tasks performed over time, and collects vast amounts of personal data crucial for intelligent time management. By using this application, its creators explore how machine learning can help "nudge" people towards better decisions. Utilizing behavioral algorithms, Timeful integrates computational and psychological sciences. This gives rise to what is shaped by computational processes known as the "scalable subject" (Stark 2018). The mass collection of individual behavioral data through tools like Timeful aims to create an effective, purposeful, and competent subject whose behavior "can be steered and nudged in ways both personally gratifying and economically profitable" (Fourcade, Healy 2017).

Wajcman notes that the creators and designers of these applications emphasize only the positive aspects of intelligent planning systems and algorithmic advice in our lives, including time management. They often suggest that users can input specific personal goals, such as exercise or spending time with friends and family, select how much time they want to dedicate to these activities each week, and the app will automatically schedule the optimal time to work on these goals.

When Google acquired Timeful in 2015, Alex Gawley from Google wrote on their blog: "The Timeful team has created an impressive system that helps organize life by understanding schedules, habits, and needs." However, this portrayal is overwhelmingly positive, highlighting only the benefits while overlooking potential threats and negative consequences. Gawley noted, "You can tell Timeful that you want to exercise three times a week... and their system will

ensure you do... We are excited about all the ways we can apply Timeful's technology to products like Inbox, Calendar, and beyond, allowing us to do more work for you and let you focus on creativity, fun, and spending time with the people you care about.”

While the creators of these applications emphasize their positive aspects, it's important to consider whether they might operate similarly to platforms like Facebook or TikTok, which effectively capture our time under the guise of encouraging self-reflection via the app. This strategy can be used to learn our temporal and consumer patterns through the time we dedicate to the application. Therefore, in the next section, I will explore the potential risks of future technologies such as AI-based time management applications and the concept of the Ministry of Time.

Implications and Risks of Automating Social Time

As we navigate the possibilities of automating social time through advanced technological applications, we must critically assess the potential dangers and ethical dilemmas such technologies may pose. While the envisioned applications like the Ministry of Time suggest a streamlined and efficient future, the implications of such systems on privacy, autonomy, and societal structures are profound and multifaceted.

Privacy Concerns and Algorithmic Control

The centralization of time management, as proposed by the Ministry of Time, could lead to unprecedented levels of surveillance and control over individuals' schedules and routines. The potential for misuse of such data is significant, as it could be exploited to manipulate consumer behavior or even exert socio-political influence. Moreover, the delegation of decision-making to algorithms raises concerns about the transparency and fairness of the processes that shape public and private life.

Cognitive Capitalism and Its Discontents

Taking a critical time study and critical algorithm studies perspective, I can argue that instead of serving user needs, these tools might serve corporate interests, fostering a form of cognitive capitalism. A significant risk is the deepening of a scenario where personal data is commodified, and individual behaviors are monetized by corporate interests. This form of capitalism not only threatens personal privacy but also risks transforming human agency into an algorithmically managed resource. AI time-automated applications could lead to increased

work and consumption, as tools designed to streamline life often end up dictating a consumerist style of living. The lack of trust in these systems' objectivity and their usage of data is not unjustified. Algorithms used by social networks provide a good example of the dangers associated with data collection mechanisms built into applications. The usage of this data to shape opinions and personalize advertising is already widely known. In the era of cognitive capitalism, it is expected that the data collected by our virtual assistants on our time organization patterns will also be subject to trade. As the saying "Time is money" created our capitalistic way of thinking, a new way of thinking about time, disconnected from monetary values, is necessary if we aim to create a healthier perspective on time management.

Loss of Human Agency, Autonomy, and Freedom

As intelligent systems take over more of our decision-making processes, there is a genuine risk of diminishing human agency. The reliance on digital assistants and smart applications to manage everyday tasks could reduce our ability to make independent choices, potentially leading to a societal shift where personal freedoms are significantly constrained by the technology we adopt. "Time cyborg" technologies could strip us of our ability to manage our own time, with decision-making increasingly subsumed by automated systems. This encroachment threatens to erode personal autonomy, as delegating time management to AI tools may prioritize efficiency over individual freedom, ultimately reshaping human identity and societal structures in profound and potentially irreversible ways.

The concept also harbors significant risks concerning privacy and the extensive control given to algorithms. The Ministry of Time would potentially gather and manage extensive data on individuals' time, using it to influence and control societal rhythms through automated decision-making systems. Such a concentration of power could lead to discomfort and resistance among the public, who may fear the violation of their privacy and autonomy. The fear is that such a system, while designed to be beneficial, could also intrude on personal liberties and be manipulated for less altruistic purposes, subtly shaping user behavior and leading to a loss of autonomy.

Ethical and Social Considerations

The ethical implications of automated time management extend beyond privacy and autonomy. They involve critical questions about the kind of society we want to build. Do we

value efficiency over freedom? Is the synchronization of societal rhythms worth the potential cost to individual spontaneity and diversity? These are pivotal considerations as we stand on the brink of significant technological integration into our daily lives.

Public Discourse and Regulation

Amidst these technological advancements, public discourse and legal frameworks struggle to keep pace with the rapid development of AI and automated systems. Recent changes in the EU AI Act reflect a growing awareness of these issues, emphasizing the need for transparency, accountability, and explainability in automated decision-making processes.

By addressing these concerns head-on, we can better navigate the complex interplay between technology and the temporal rhythms of society, ensuring that innovations in time management serve the public good without compromising fundamental human rights (Züger, Asghari 2023).

Opportunities: A New Concept of AI Time – Graph Time

In concluding this article, I want to represent my concept of aiTime. The vision of aiTime involves leveraging AI to create sophisticated models of temporal management that go beyond traditional linear or pointillist views of time. One such model is Graph Time, which proposes a more structured yet flexible approach to managing temporal rhythms.

Graph Time: A New Temporal Framework

Graph Time envisions time as a network of interconnected nodes and edges, representing events and the relationships between them. This model allows for a more nuanced understanding of time, accommodating the complexity and variability of modern life. Nodes symbolize key events or tasks, while edges represent the connections and dependencies between these events.

This concept aligns with the idea of creating algorithmic infrastructures for human flourishing, where AI not only optimizes efficiency but also promotes a balanced and sustainable approach to time management. By visualizing time as a graph, we can better understand and manage the multiple, often conflicting, temporal rhythms that characterize contemporary society.

Illustration 1: Graph time represented along the horizontal axis

Algorithmic Coordination and Personalization

AI can play a crucial role in realizing Graph Time by providing tools for algorithmic coordination and personalization. These tools can analyze vast amounts of data to identify patterns and optimize schedules, ensuring that individuals can balance work, leisure, and personal responsibilities more effectively. For instance, AI could adjust public transportation schedules based on real-time data, reducing congestion and improving efficiency.

Towards a Sustainable Ecology of Time

Graph Time also emphasizes the importance of sustainability in time management. By promoting an "ecology of time," AI can help design systems that prioritize human well-being and environmental sustainability. This involves creating work schedules that minimize stress and burnout, encouraging a healthier work-life balance.

Conclusion: Envisioning a Harmonious Temporal Future

The concept of Graph Time represents a visionary approach to temporal management, leveraging AI to create a more structured and flexible temporal framework. As we navigate the complexities of modern life, Graph Time offers a way to harmonize the diverse rhythms of our daily activities, fostering a balanced and sustainable approach to managing time.

Ultimately, the realization of Graph Time requires a collective effort to embrace innovation while safeguarding the values and principles that underpin our society. By fostering a culture of collaboration, inclusivity, and ethical governance, we can pave the way for a future

where time is not just a resource to be managed but a domain for human flourishing and creativity.

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